

Effect of blast (BI) on IR50 in late samba

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In late samba 1983 there was a severe BI outbreak on IR50 in Kancheepuram taluk of Chingleput District. We observed IR50, IET1722, IR20, Ponni and CO 37, planted in a 25-ha area, for infection caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*.

Five 1-m² microplots were marked out in each 1-acre field. Five plots were selected 1 m away from the center of each bund and one plot was in the center of the field. Disease intensity was assessed by randomly selecting 25 leaves/plot and grading them on the scale

Table 1. Scaling system for BI infection, Chingleput, India.

Grade	1	3	5	7	9
Intensity of infection (70 area affected)	<1	1-5	6-25	26-50	>50

shown in Table 1.

After determining the level of infection, disease index was calculated:

$$DI = \frac{\text{Sum of } n \times (v)}{N \times V} \times 100$$

where n = number of leaves at each infection level, v = the grade for each group of leaves, V = the highest grade allotted in the score chart, and N = total number of leaves observed.

IR50 planted on 14 Sep escaped BI infection, but the late samba crop was severely infected (Table 2). Other

Table 2. BI incidence for different varieties, Chingleput, India.

Variety	Planting date	Crop stage	Disease index
IR50	14 Sep 1983	Maturity	16.9
IR50	13 Oct	Dough	66.8
IET1722	13 Oct	Dough	22.9
IR20	13 Oct	Dough	1.7
IR50	21 Oct	Dough	58.4
Ponni	21 Oct	Booting	1.7
IR20	21 Oct	Booting	0.8
C037	21 Oct	Booting	2.6

varieties, except IET1722, had a high degree of BI resistance. □

Screening rice for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is one of the most important rice pests in China. We studied the response to BPH of rice varieties at different ages in the field and in the greenhouse (Table 1).

In the field, test varieties were planted in a randomized block design in three replications. Two rows of susceptible TN1 were grown between test varieties. Decamethrin, a BPH-resurgence-inducing insecticide, was sprayed on TN1 at 10 g ai/ha 30 d after transplanting (DT). Varieties were scored for resistance at 60, 65, and 70 DT (Table 2).

In the greenhouse test to determine

the effect of plant age on BPH resistance, test varieties were sown in 60- × 45- × 10-cm seedboxes. Each line was planted

in 20-cm rows at 5-cm spacing in 3 replications. Seedlings at different plant ages were infested with 2d- or 3d-

Table 2. Field resistance of rice varieties to BPH, Guangzhou, China.

Variety	Damage rating			Insects ^a (no./hill)	
	60 DT	65 DT	70 DT	60 DT	70 DT
TN1	7	8.3	9	139.9 a	212.5 a
Kencana	1	1	5.7	48.7 ab	96.9 bc
Baosyan 2	1	1.7	5.7	87 a	82.6 bc
Triveni	1	1	2.3	19.1 c	53 c
Utri Rajapan	1	1	1	22.7 ab	134.4 b
Fubaoai 21	1	1	5.7	61.9 ab	87.7 bc
ASD7	1	1	1.7	12.5 c	25.5 c
IR46	1	1	1	9 c	50 c
IR26	1	1	1.7	15.9 c	25.4 c
Sinna Sivappu	1	1	1	9.6 c	30.7 c
7105	1	1	1	9.9 c	41.5 c

^aIn a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 3. BPH resistance of rice varieties at six plant ages in the greenhouse, Guangzhou, China.

Variety	Damage rating											
	6 DI ^a						8 DI					
	7	10	15	20	30	45	7	10	15	20	30	45
TN1	9	9	5.7	9	6.3	4.5	9	9	9	9	8.3	7.7
Kencana	6.3	7.7	4.3	4.3	3.7	3.7	8.3	9	5	4.3	5.7	5.7
Baosyan 2	6.3	6.3	1.7	2.3	1.7	1.7	9	8.3	3	2.3	2.7	3
Triveni	3	3.7	1	1	1	1	7.7	6.3	1	1	1	1
Utri Rajapan	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.3	1	1	6.3	4.3	3.6	3.7	1	1
Fubaoai 21	5.7	6.3	1.7	2.3	1.7	2.3	9	8.3	3	2.3	2.3	3.7
ASD7	1	1	1	1	1	1	1.7	1	1	1	1	1
IR46	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
IR26	1	1.7	1	1	1	1	1.7	1.7	1	1	1	1
Sinna Sivappu	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

^a DI = days after infestation.

Table 1. Rice varieties with different genes for BPH resistance were evaluated in Guangzhou, China.

Variety	Resistance gene
IR26, IR46, 7105	<i>Bph</i> 1
ASD7	<i>bph</i> 2
Sinna Sivappu	2 unidentified genes
Kencana, Triveni, Utri Rajapan, Fubaoai 21, Baosyan 2	Minor gene
TN1	No resistance